

Representing the Emerging Field of Health Sciences from a Librarian's Perspective: The Example of the University of Lucerne

In a paper published in *Gesundheitswesen* in 2016 [1] it has been suggested that the field of health sciences can be represented according to: 1) a specification of the content of the field in terms of people's health needs and the societal responses to them; 2) a meta-level framework to exhaustively represent the range of other scientific disciplines engaged in health research; and 3) a heuristic framework for the specification of a set of shared methodological approaches relevant across the range of these disciplines. Such a conception accords to the proposed domains of the two main areas of the field of health sciences (see Table 1 of the publication in *Gesundheitswesen* [1]), providing a sound starting point for the representation of health sciences in the ontology of scientific disciplines.

From a librarian's perspective the concrete challenge is how to best represent the domains of health sciences with their many interdisciplinary bearings in an already existing universal classification system [2] according to librarian standards. On the one hand the classification has to be comprehensive to include all essential aspects of health sciences in their self-conception, on the other hand – as part of a universal classification system - health sciences should be distinguishable from other related fields such as medicine, social sciences and humanities. The arrangement, moreover, has to be comprehensible to users. Finally, the classification has to be relatively stable and retain consistency with the terminological development of the discipline.

Below we present the draft proposal developed by the library of the University of Lucerne for classifying the domains of health sciences within the RVK (Regensburger Verbundklassifikation) classification system. Approval for full integration of the proposal into RVK is pending. We kindly invite comments and suggestions concerning our proposition.

References:

1 *Stucki G, Rubinelli S, Reinhardt JD, Bickenbach JE*. Towards a Common Understanding of the Health Sciences. *Gesundheitswesen* 2016; 78:1-5.

2 At the University Library of Lucerne the "Regensburger Verbundklassifikation" is in use: <http://rvk.uni-regensburg.de/>

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Current proposal from a librarian perspective (in German and English)

MT 1000 **Zeitschriften (Journals)**

MT 1100 – MT 1190 **Allgemeines (general)**

MT 1100 **Nachschlagewerke (reference texts)**

MT 1120 **Einführungen (introductory texts)**

MT 1140 **Bibliographien (bibliographies)**

MT 1160 **Grundlagen und Selbstverständnis der Gesundheitswissenschaften
(foundation and identity of the health sciences)**

MT 1200 – MT 1240 **Geschichte der Gesundheit und der
Gesundheitswissenschaften (history of health and the health sciences)**

MT 1200 **Allgemeines (general)**

MT 1210 **nach Ländern (CSN des Namens) (geographical aspects)**

- MT 1220 – MT 1230 nach Perioden (chronological aspects)
- MT 1220 Antike (-500) (antiquity)
 - MT 1225 Mittelalter (500-1500) (middle ages)
 - MT 1230 Neuzeit (1500-) (modern age)
- MT 1240 Einzelthemen (special topics)
- MT 1250 Studium der Gesundheitswissenschaften (studying health sciences)**
- MT 1260 – MT 1280 Sammelwerke (collected editions)**
- MT 1260 Aufsatzsammlungen mehrerer Autoren (collection with several contributors)
 - MT 1270 Gesammelte Aufsätze eines Autors (collection with a single contributor)
 - MT 1280 Kongressberichte (congress volumes)
- MT 1290 Sonstige allgemeine Themen (other issues)**

MT 1300 Assoziierte Gebiete der biomedizinischen und klinisch-medizinischen Wissenschaften (associated fields of the biomedical and clinical-medical sciences)

MT 1400 – MT 1900 Gebiete in den Gesundheitswissenschaften (fields in the health sciences)

MT 1400 Allgemeines und Gebietsübergreifendes (general and cross topic issues)

MT 1420 Philosophie der Gesundheit (philosophy of health)

Philosophie (philosophy) (→ CC 6600, CC 7260 – CC 7267)

MT 1440 Gesundheitssoziologie (health sociology)

Soziologie (sociology) (→ MS 6000 – MS 6320)

MT 1460 *Public health* (public health)

Öffentliche Verwaltung (public administration) (→ MF 7000 – MF 7800)

Medizin (medicine) (→ XF)

MT 1480 Gesundheitsökonomie (health economics)

Ökonomie (economics) (→ QX 700 – QX 795, QX 900)

MT 1500 Gesundheitspolitik (health policy)

- Politikwissenschaft (political sciences) (→ MF 9200, MK 8200)
- MT 1520 Gesundheitsmanagement (health management)**
Betriebswirtschaft (management sciences) (→ QQ)
- MT 1540 Gesundheitsverhalten (health behaviour)**
Verhaltenswissenschaften (behavioural sciences) (→ CZ 1200)
Psychologie (psychology) (→ CW)
- MT 1560 Gesundheitserziehung (health education)**
Erziehungswissenschaften (educational sciences) (→ DO 7000 – DO 7009)
- MT 1580 Gesundheitskommunikationswissenschaften (health communication sciences)**
Kommunikationswissenschaften (communication sciences) (→ AP)
- MT 1600 Health Technology and Impact Assessment (Health Technology and Impact Assessment (HTA) and (HIA))**
Kommunikationswissenschaften (communication sciences) (→ AP)
Öffentliche Verwaltung (public administration) (→ MF 7000 – MF 7800)
- MT 1620 Gesundheitsinformatik (health informatics)**
Informatik (informatics) (→ ST 600 – ST 690)
Computer sciences (→ ST)
- MT 1640 Epidemiologie (Epidemiology)**
Medizin (medicine) (→ XF 4100 – XF 4199)
- MT 1660 Biostatistik (biostatistics)**
Statistik (statistics) (→ WC 7700)
Mathematik (mathematics) (→ WC 7000)
- MT 1680 Ethik in der Gesundheitsversorgung (health care ethics)**
Sozialethik (social ethics) (→ CC 7260 – CC 7267)
- MT 1900 Sonstige Gebiete in den Gesundheitswissenschaften (other fields in health sciences)**
- MT 2000 – MT 2300 Methoden der Gesundheitswissenschaften (methods in health sciences)**
- MT 2000 Allgemeines (general)**
- MT 2050 Prinzipien von Studien mit Menschen (principles of conducting studies with humans)**

- MT 2100 Forschungsdesign (**research design**)
- MT 2150 Quantitative Methoden (**quantitative methods**)
- MT 2200 Qualitative Methoden (**qualitative methods**)
- MT 2300 Sonstige Methoden der Gesundheitswissenschaften (**other methods in health sciences**)
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- MT 2500 – MT 2900 Fähigkeiten in den Gesundheitswissenschaften (**skills in the health sciences**)
- MT 2500 Allgemeines (**general**)
- MT 2520 Management von klinischen Studien (**clinical trial management**)
- MT 2540 Management von Umfragen in den Gesundheitswissenschaften (**management of surveys in the health sciences**)
- MT 2560 Projekt Management in den Gesundheitswissenschaften (**project management in the health sciences**)
- MT 2580 Datenbank und Datenmanagement in den Gesundheitswissenschaften (**database and data management in the health sciences**)
- MT 2600 Statistisches Programmieren in den Gesundheitswissenschaften (**statistical programming in the health sciences**)
- MT 2620 Kritisches Denken, Lesen, Argumentieren und Schreiben in den Gesundheitswissenschaften (**critical thinking, reading, argumentation and writing in the health sciences**)
- MT 2640 Protokollentwicklung und Antragstellung in den Gesundheitswissenschaften (**protocol and grant development in the health sciences**)
- MT 2660 Wissenschaftliche Publikationen, Berichte und Präsentationen in den Gesundheitswissenschaften (**scientific publications, reports and presentations in the health sciences**)
- MT 2680 Wissenstransfer in den Gesundheitswissenschaften (**knowledge transfer in the health sciences**)
- MT 2900 Sonstige Fähigkeiten in den Gesundheitswissenschaften (**other skills in the health sciences**)

MT 3000 – MT 3900 Funktionsfähigkeit und Gesundheit der Person im Kontext (a person's functioning and health in context)

MT 3000 Allgemeines (general)

MT 3100 – MT 3180 Operationalisierung von Funktionsfähigkeit und Gesundheit (operationalization of health)

MT 3100 Allgemeines (general)

MT 3120 Definitionen von Gesundheit (definitions of health)

MT 3140 Konzepte von Gesundheit (conceptualizations of health)

MT 3160 Klassifikationen von Gesundheit (classifications of health)

MT 3180 Messung von Gesundheit (measurement of health)

MT 3200 Funktionsfähigkeit und Gesundheit (functioning and health)

MT 3300 Funktionsfähigkeit und Gesundheitsstörungen (functioning and health conditions)

MT 3400 Funktionsfähigkeit und Person (functioning and person)

MT 3500 Funktionsfähigkeit und Umfeld (functioning and society)

MT 3600 Funktionsfähigkeit und Lebensqualität (functioning and quality of life)

MT 3900 Einzelthemen (special topics)

MT 4000 – MT 5000 Gesundheitssystem (health system)

MT 4000 – MT 4040 Allgemeines (general)

MT 4000 Gesamtdarstellungen (general works)

MT 4020 Werte und Ziele im Gesundheitssystem (values and goals in the health system)

MT 4040 Leistungsfähigkeit des Gesundheitssystems (health systems performance)

MT 4100 *Public Policy*, Recht und Governance im Gesundheitssystem (public policy, law and governance in the health system)

MT 4200 Gesundheitsversorgung und Finanzierung (service provision and finance)

MT 4300 Personen-bezogene Leistungserbringung durch Gesundheitsfachleute (service delivery in health professional - person interaction)

- MT 4400 Information im Gesundheitssystem (information in the health system)**
- MT 4500 – MT 4590 Gesundheitsinterventionen (health interventions)**
- MT 4500 Allgemeines (general)
 - MT 4520 Medizinische und chirurgische Interventionen (medical and surgical interventions)
 - MT 4540 *Public Health* Interventionen (public health interventions)
 - MT 4560 Interventionen zur Optimierung der Funktionsfähigkeit (functioning interventions)
 - MT 4590 Sonstige Gesundheitsinterventionen (other health interventions)
- MT 4600 Produkte, Prozeduren und Technologien im Gesundheitssystem (products, procedures and technologies in the health system)**
- MT 4700 Human Resources im Gesundheitssystem (human resources in the health system)**
- MT 4800 – MT 4880 Akteure im Gesundheitssystem (actors in the health system)**
- MT 4800 Allgemeines (general)
 - MT 4820 – MT 4830 Nichtregierungsorganisationen (non-governmental organizations in the health system)
 - MT 4820 Allgemeines (general)
 - MT 4825 Berichte (reports)
 - MT 4830 Einzelthemen (special topics)
 - MT 4840 – MT 4860 Öffentliche Verwaltung im Gesundheitssystem (public administration in the health system)
 - MT 4840 Allgemeines (general)
 - MT 4845 Berichte (reports)
 - MT 4850 Einzelthemen (special topics)
 - MT 4860 – MT 4870 Privatwirtschaft (private organizations in the health system)
 - MT 4860 Allgemeines (general)
 - MT 4865 Berichte (reports)
 - MT 4870 Einzelthemen (special topics)
 - MT 4880 Sonstige Akteure (other actors)
- MT 4900 – MT 4990 Andere gesellschaftliche Systeme in Interaktion mit dem Gesundheitssystem (other societal systems in interaction with the health system)**
- MT 4900 Allgemeines (general)

MT 4920	Arbeit und Gesundheit (labor and the health system)
MT 4940	Soziales und Gesundheit (social affairs and the health system)
MT 4960	Bildung und Gesundheit (education and the health system)
MT 4990	Sonstige gesellschaftliche Systeme (other societal systems)
MT 5000	Einzelthemen (special topics)